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Chief Editor
Dr. J.B. Helonde

Executive Editor
Mr. Somil Mayur Shah

ABSTRACT

Wheel assembly is a major part of automotive design which connects the wheel to the suspension system and therefore transfers the force from road to the suspension components. It also holds the brake system as well as facilitates steering of the vehicle. Power train department is also concerned with the transmission of power from engine to wheels.

Aim of the report is to describe the process and simulation that goes into designing of hub, upright and differential mounting of a formula student car as well as calculating the size of sprocket for maximum acceleration.

1. INTRODUCTION**1.1 Problem Definition**

Power train is that department of the car concerned with delivering the power from engine to the wheels. Every power transmitting element from engine to wheels are included in the department. It deals with the design, manufacturing and assembly of hubs, uprights, differential mounts, axle, differential, wheels and tires. These components play an important role in deciding the speed, acceleration and mass of the car. Components are designed and assembled after co-ordinating with suspension, chassis, brake and steering department.

1.2 Project Objectives

The project aimed to reduce the difficulties faced during the assembly in 2018 car and to completely eliminate the failures incurred in the assembly. To accomplish that object, a series of measures were taken from changing the arrangement of bearing to manufacturing hubs of steel instead of aluminium.

1.3 Design Constraints and considerations

The project was designed in compliance with the rules of Formula Bharat 2020 for participation in the same. The major design considerations in this year's car are as follows

- Packaging in 10'' wheels
- Reduction in unsprung mass
- Better acceleration
- Ease in assembly and disassembly
- Better locking of bearing to reduce backlash
- Adjustable differential mounting
- Ease of manufacturing of components

2. BEARING SELECTION

A pair of single row tapered roller bearing is used in back-to-back arrangement compared to previous car's face-to-face arrangement. For both tapered roller and angular contact ball bearings, the distance L between the pressure centres is longer when the bearings are arranged back -to -back compared with bearings arranged face to face. This means that bearings arranged back-to -back can accommodate relatively large tilting moments even if the distance between the bearing centres is relatively short. They are designed to accommodate combined loads, i.e. simultaneously acting radial and axial loads. Matched bearings arranged back-to-back have load lines that diverge toward the bearing axis to provide a relatively stiff bearing arrangement that can also accommodate tilting moments. Axial loads in both directions can be accommodated, but only by one bearing in each direction.

After careful consideration, it was decided that 320-32X bearing be used as the load ratings of bearing were well above the load on hubs and uprights and the size of bearing was optimum.

Bearing details

ID - 32mm, OD – 58mm, Width – 17mm

Dynamic load rating – 36.9 KN, Static load rating – 46.5 KN

Fig.1

3. 3.WHEELS AND TIRES

Keizer 10'' aluminium wheels are used for lighter weight, lower CG and higher rollover stability. Wheels are custom designed for required offset, lug bolts size and PCD. PCD is 90mm which reduces the weight of hub.

Hoosier soft compound wet tires are being used for better grip and all weather purpose. We also have a set of Carlisle wet tires (205/50-10).

4. DIFFERENTIAL AND DIFFERENTIAL MOUNTING

Dry open type differential is being used instead of limited slip differential as it serves the purpose of providing grip and better handling and stability on a dry track and it is cost efficient at the same time. Sprocket mounted on the differential have teeth machined to our needs. Below is the calculation for required number of teeth.

400kg assumed mass

Coefficient of friction = 1

$F = un = 4000 \text{ N}$

Tire radius = 0.2286m

$T = 4000 * 0.2286 = 914.4$

Front sprocket teeth = 16

Rear sprocket teeth = x

60N.m = torque produced by engine

77/39 = primary drive ratio

39/14 = 1st gear ratio

$60 * (77/39) * (39/14) * (x/16) = 914.4$

X = 45

There are 52 teeth in the sprocket for better acceleration.

Differential mountings are adjustable with fixed mounting at one end and adjustable at other end with rod ends. They are made of Al 6061 (yield strength – 275 mpa) which suffice our strength requirements and is lightweight at the same time. Load acting on the differential mounting is only the weight of differential. Radial ball bearing 61907 is used to support the differential as axial loads acting on the mountings are very low and it can easily withstand load of differential. The bearings are stopped by providing retaining rings on either side of bearings.

Fig.2

Table.1

Constraints	Mounting surfaces
Forces	Bearing surface
Magnitude	500 N
deformation	5.9e-6 m
Equivalent stress	4.67e6 Pa

Using spool was another option but the main shortcoming of spool is that it can cause the rear of the vehicle to spin out, fish-tale or can cause lot of noise because of twisting and release of axles. This can also lead to breaking of axles eventually. It can also lead to wear in tires. On the other hand, open differential is advantageous for following reason.

- Allows for completely different wheel speeds on the same axle, meaning no wheel slip will occur while going around a corner, as the outside tyre will travel further.

Fig 3

Fig 4

5. AXLE

Axle used in the prototype vehicle are plunge joint and rzeppa cv joint on the same shaft. Plunge joint is used on the differential side which provides axial adjustment of the axle. Rzeppa joint is used on the wheel side of the axle providing angular adjustments for better fitting while acting as cv joint at the same time.

6. HUBS

6.1. Introduction

Hub is that component of the assembly responsible for connecting wheels to the suspension system. Hubs are directly mounted to the wheels and transfers the power from axles to wheels. Hubs are supported by wheel bearings on uprights. Brake rotors are also mounted on hubs and it has internal splines to fit the axle.

6.2. Method

The design of the wheel hub is dependent on the following factors

- PCD of the wheel mounting plate
- Bearing used
- PCD of brake rotors
- Locking methods of bearing
- Front or rear hub
- Size of brake caliper
 - a. wheel mounting plate is decided by the PCD of lug bolts. This is the first step in creating the design of hub in 3D modelling software.
 - b. Shaft connecting the wheel mounting plate and brake rotor mounting plate. Width is decided by the size of brake caliper and diameter by performing iterations in simulation software for required strength.
 - c. Brake rotor mounting plate is decided by PCD of brake rotors.
 - d. Bearing collar for mounting of bearing. Width is dependent on size of brake caliper and diameter on ID of bearing used.
 - e. Bearing shaft used to mount the bearings and to transfer the load to suspension system. Diameter depends on ID of bearing and width on locking method used.

Fig.5

The wheel hub has to be strong enough to withstand the following forces

- Force due to acceleration or deceleration
- Cornering
- Wheel travel or bump
- Brake torque or torque from the axles

6.3. Front hub

The sole function of the front hub is to support the wheels and connect it to the suspension system. Front hub is non-power transmitting component hence it doesn't have splines to fit the axle. Bearings in the front assembly are locked with the help of a lock nut for which threads are provided on the shaft of front hub and a slot for tab washer.

Fig.6

6.4. Rear hub

The function of the rear hub is to support the wheels and connect it to the suspension system as well as transmitting the power from axle to wheel. For that purpose, rear hubs have internal splines to fit the axle and to transmit the power. Bearing in the rear assembly is locked by retaining ring hence a groove is machined on the shaft to place ring.

Fig 7

Fig.8

6.5. Material selection

SS 304

Table.2

Young's modulus	200Gpa
Elongation at break	8%
Fatigue strength	210Mpa
Poisson's ratio	0.28
Shear strength	400Mpa
Tensile strength	580Mpa
Yield strength	230Mpa

AISI 4340

Table.3

Young's modulus	190Gpa
Elongation at break	12%
Fatigue strength	330Mpa
Poisson's ratio	0.29
Shear strength	430Mpa
Tensile strength	690Mpa
Yield strength	470Mpa

Hubs are made of AISI 4340 as it has high tensile and fatigue strength which are desirable properties for manufacturing of splines.

6.6. Analysis

The force due to braking in the longitudinal direction is calculated as follows

Stopping distance, $s = 5\text{m}$

Initial velocity, $u = 13.8\text{m/s}$

Mass of the car, $m = 350\text{kg}$

Calculating deceleration by $v^2 - u^2 = 2 \cdot a \cdot s$

$$a = -19\text{m/s}^2$$

assuming 60% weight transfer to the front, force due to the braking on front hub = 3990N

force due to cornering in lateral direction

Skid pad track diameter, $\varnothing = 15.25\text{ m} \Rightarrow r = 9.125\text{ m}$

Width of track = 3 m

Travelling distance = $d = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot r$

$$2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot 9.125 = 57.33\text{m}$$

Taking $t = 7\text{ sec}$ for one lap

$$v = \frac{d}{t} = \frac{57.33}{7} = 8.19\text{ m/sec}$$

$$a = \frac{v^2}{r} = \frac{8.19^2}{9.125} = 7.35\text{ m/sec}^2$$

$f = 2600\text{N}$

Considering the weight of the car, bump force = 2000N.

The FEM analysis was done on ANSYS workbench and the results were carried out as follows
 Quadratic method is used to generate the mesh with an element size of 5mm.

Table.4

Details of "Force"	
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	2 Faces
Definition	
Type	Force
Define By	Components
Coordinate System	Global Coordinate System
<input type="checkbox"/> X Component	3990. N (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Y Component	2000. N (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Z Component	2600. N (ramped)
Suppressed	No

Table.5

Constraints	Wheel mounting points
Force	Shaft
Equivalent stress	2.736e+008 Pa
Maximum deformation	1.309e-004 m
FOS (ultimate)	2.72

Maximum stress is generated at the edge of wheel mounting points and maximum deformation occurs at the tip of the shaft. The design is safe.

Moment generated at wheel mounting points during braking is calculated as follows
Force due to braking is longitudinal direction = 3990 N

tire radius = 0.2286 m

Moment generated $\approx 900\text{Nm}$

Quadratic method is used to generate the mesh with an element size of 5mm.

Fig 9

Fig 10

Fig 11

Fig 12

Fig 13

Fig 14

Table.6

Details of "Moment"	
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	8 Faces
Definition	
Type	Moment
Define By	Vector
<input type="checkbox"/> Magnitude	900. N-m (ramped)
Direction	Click to Change
Suppressed	No
Behavior	Deformable
Advanced	

Table.7

Constraints	Brake rotor mounting points
Force	Wheel mounting points
Equivalent stress	1.4436e+008 Pa
Maximum deformation	8.8444e-005 m
FOS (ultimate)	5.32

Maximum stress is generated at wheel mounting points and maximum deformation occurs at outer edge of wheel mounting points.

Moment generated at brake rotor mounting points while braking is calculated as follows

After consulting the brake department, clamping force was found to be = 1302 N

Moment generated at the front wheels = 115.5Nm

Quadratic method is used to generate the mesh with an element size of 5mm.

Table.8

Details of "Moment"	
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	8 Faces
Definition	
Type	Moment
Define By	Vector
<input type="checkbox"/> Magnitude	115.5 N-m (ramped)
Direction	Click to Change
Suppressed	No
Behavior	Deformable
Advanced	

Table.9

Constraints	Wheel mounting points
Force	Brake rotor mounting points
Equivalent stress	1.8872e+007 Pa
Maximum deformation	8.9063e-006 m
FOS (ultimate)	41.8

The value of FOS is much greater than required value because the thickness of mounting plate is greater than required. This was necessary to fit the caliper because increase in shaft length would have led to more deformation.

7. UPRIGHTS

7.1. Introduction

Upright is that component of the assembly which houses wheel bearings, supports hub, brake caliper and connects wheel to suspension and steering system. All the forces travels from hub to upright to the suspension system. It also has to withstand torque from brake caliper and latitudinal force on tie-rod mounting. Hence upright has to have enough strength to withstand these forces.

7.2. Method

The design of upright is dependent on following factors.

- Kpi
- Caster
- Bearings
- Distance between l_{bj} and u_{bj}
- Locking method of bearing
- Brake caliper
- Tie rod mounting

The design process starts by deciding the kingpin inclination, caster and distance between upper ball joint and lower ball joint. The next step is designing the bearing housing after deciding the tolerances, bearing arrangement and locking method. A step is provided in the middle of the bearing housing to axially locate the bearing and the step is discontinuous to facilitate easy removal of bearing.

Fig.15

After the design of housing, clamps are designed and holes are provided for the wishbones from KPI and caster. Then comes the mounting for brake caliper which are designed with the help of CAD model of the caliper. The final step is to design the mounting for the tie-rods which are decided from the steering geometry.

The upright has to be strong enough to withstand following forces

- Longitudinal force while braking
- Latitudinal force while cornering
- Bump force
- Moment generated at brake caliper mountings while braking
- Force on tie rod mounting while cornering

7.3. Front upright

The front upright is designed to withstand more cornering forces due to steering. Hence it was decided to use 2 single row tapered roller bearing with back to back arrangement. Also the tie rod mounting was designed in accordance with ackerman geometry.

Fig.16

7.4. Rear upright

The design of rear upright started by deciding to use radial ball bearing as axial forces on the rear wheel are low. The initial design looked as follows.

Fig.17

But there were some drawbacks in the design. The strength of the upright was very low and the length of brackets had to be long to fit the wishbones which decreased the strength even further, so it was decided to use the design as same as front with some changes in the tie rod mounting.

Fig.18

7.5. Material selection

Table.10

Al 7050

Young's modulus	70 Gpa
Elongation at break	2.2%
Fatigue strength	130 Mpa
Poisson's ratio	0.32
Shear strength	280 Mpa
Tensile strength	490 Mpa
Yield strength	390 Mpa

Table.11

Al 7075-T6

Young's modulus	70 Gpa
Elongation at break	7.9%
Fatigue strength	160 Mpa
Poisson's ratio	0.32
Shear strength	330 Mpa
Tensile strength	560 Mpa
Yield strength	480 Mpa

Uprights are manufactured from 7075-T6 billets as it's tensile strength and fatigue strength is greater than that of 7050.

7.6. Analysis

As we've calculated before,
 longitudinal force during braking = 3990 N
 latitudinal force during cornering = 2600 N
 bump force = 2000 N

The FEM analysis was done on ANSYS workbench and the results were carried out as follows
 Quadratic method is used to generate the mesh with an element size of 5mm.

Table.12

Details of "Force"	
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	2 Faces
Definition	
Type	Force
Define By	Components
Coordinate System	Global Coordinate System
<input type="checkbox"/> X Component	3990. N (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Y Component	2000. N (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Z Component	2600. N (ramped)
Suppressed	No

Table.13

Constraints	Wishbone mounting points
Force	Bearing housing
Equivalent stress	8.5549e+007 Pa
Maximum deformation	5.3979e-005 m
FOS (ultimate)	6.7

Moment generated at brake caliper mounting points = 115.5Nm
 Quadratic method is used to generate the mesh with an element size of 5mm.

Table.14

Details of "Moment"	
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	4 Faces
Definition	
Type	Moment
Define By	Components
Coordinate System	Global Coordinate System
<input type="checkbox"/> X Component	0. N-m (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Y Component	0. N-m (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Z Component	-115.5 N-m (ramped)
Suppressed	No
Behavior	Deformable
Advanced	

Table.15

Constraints	Wishbone mounting points
Force	Brake caliper mounting
Equivalent stress	4.7813e+007 Pa
Maximum deformation	5.346e-005 m
FOS (ultimate)	12.12

Fig 19

Fig 20

Fig 21

Fig 22

Force due to cornering on tie rod mounting = 2600N
 Quadratic method is used to generate the mesh with an element size of 5mm

Table.16

Constraints	Bearing housing
Force	Tie rod mounting
Equivalent stress	5.8464e+007 Pa
Maximum deformation	7.2529e-005 m
FOS (ultimate)	9.8

Table.17

Details of "Force"	
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	4 Faces
Definition	
Type	Force
Define By	Components
Coordinate System	Global Coordinate System
<input type="checkbox"/> X Component	0. N (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Y Component	0. N (ramped)
<input type="checkbox"/> Z Component	-2600. N (ramped)
Suppressed	No

Fig 23

Fig 24

Fig 25

Fig 26

8. CONCLUSION

The following results were obtained from the report

1. Better acceleration by calculating number of teeth on sprocket
2. Efficient locking and placement of bearing to reduce backlash
3. Development of accurate FEA model with the help of calculations
4. To design adjustable differential mounting.

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